

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CLIMATE CHANGE AND FOOD SECURITY IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA

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Sylvester Ohiomu, PhD¹ and Patience Lilian Ozor, PhD²

Abstract

The soaring cases of coronavirus pandemic coupled with unpredictable climatic variations pose danger to human lives and food security. This work examines the relationship between climate change and food security in Sub-Saharan Africa. Using the Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) technique with preliminary diagnostic tests on panel data across the 17 Sub-Sahara African countries, the dependent variable is agricultural output (AGROP), while the independent variables are temperature (TEMP), rainfall (RFALL), government expenditure on agriculture, (GEA), inflation (INFL), exchange rate (EXR), gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) and labour force (LABF). The findings reveal that climate change exerts a negative impact on food security through temperature variations that degenerated during the period under review. The results also showed a positive, significant impact of government expenditure, which increased during the period of the study. The work recommends that the government should embark on massive productive investments to reinvigorate and re-engineer the economy. The government and appropriate agencies should also put in place hybrid technology of high-yield crops adaptive to changes in climate as well as effective mechanisms for food storage to secure food for the future.

Keywords: Food Security, Climate change, Economic growth, GMM

JEL Classification: D13, Q12, Q18, Q54

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Introduction

Climate change has ignited global uncertainty and unpredictable climatic variations that pose danger to human lives, animals, plants and economic activities in global and national economies. This debilitating climate change has implications on the economies of nations across the globe, with excruciating effects on Sub-Saharan Africa. Climate change has also affected human lives and food security in Africa. This has become worrisome and a source of deep concern to economists, policymakers and citizens at all levels. Climate change is one of the most prominent problems facing the contemporary global community today. The attention it has drawn from international organisations (such as the United Nations, the European Union and the African Union), through treaties, agreements and action plans to combat its growing threat, coupled with the growing body of research on the issue, attests to its gravity. Among other institutional frameworks, the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the European Climate Change Programme (ECCP) of the EU and the Climate Change and Desertification Unit (CCDU) of the African Union constitute some of the most elaborate responses from the global community. Based on the foregoing discussion, it is obvious that climate change is a global problem with devastating imprints that affect the economic, social, political and environmental aspects of local communities (Ezemonye, 2019). In Nigeria, for instance, climate change has been linked with increasing cases of flooding, desertification, cattle movement towards the South-South (which in turn instigates crises among farmers and herdsman), low levels of rainfall, or irregular rainfall and low agricultural productivity, among other problems. The implications of climate change for the agricultural sector, which is largely rain-fed in Nigeria, are of paramount significance to this study.

The economic landscape of most African countries depends essentially on the dynamics of climate change. Key sectors driving their economic performance and livelihoods, such as agriculture, forestry, energy, tourism, and coastal and water resources, are highly vulnerable to climate change (Ebele and Emodi, 2016; Odusola and Abidoye 2015).

Based on the impact (established and projected) of climate change on agricultural production, it is safe to contend that in addition to the issue of food security and survival of smallholder farmers with minimal livelihood alternatives (Abdul-Razak and Kruse, 2017), what is also at stake on a larger scale is the economic growth of nation-states, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa where the agricultural sector forms the backbone of most national economies. This is so because agriculture remains the engine of economy-wide performance because this sector's growth exhibits a higher multiplier than growth in other sectors, especially in countries where its sector share is

large (Tiffin and Irz, 2006). In the long run, decreased performance in the agricultural sector posted a negative effect on the strength of the economy.

Reports from the National Centre for Disease Control and Worldometer information show a rising trend in new infections daily, which depicts the catastrophic transmission nature of the COVID-19 pandemic in Africa. COVID-19 has spread across the world since its presence was first reported in Wuhan, China, in December 2019. With its far-reaching geographical spread, the pandemic is projected to have devastating effects on the global economy, as attested by the projection of the International Monetary Fund in April 2020 that the world economy would contract sharply by 3 per cent, and that the economy of Africa would contract by 1.6 per cent in 2020 (World Bank, 2020). Furthermore, Asian Development Bank (2020) has projected that, in a worst-case scenario, economic activity for Africa as a whole would contract by 2.6 per cent, with negative impacts on the employment rate. The report also estimated that four out of five businesses in Africa would be significantly affected by the pandemic. It further predicted an economic contraction of 3.4 per cent for the continent. Hunger and shortage of food supply plague the survivors of the coronavirus pandemic; hence, the need for proactive strategies for food security is necessary.

Many countries' economies—even those in Sub-Saharan Africa—have implemented numerous containment measures to curb the spread of the virus, such as the closing of schools, restricting domestic and international travel, promoting the use of protective gear and hand hygiene, and imposing curfews and lockdowns (National Centre for Disease Control, 2020). These measures have affected these economies in various ways and have disrupted air travel, tourism, trade, business operations, agriculture, food security and global supply chains. The question that comes to mind is how one evaluate the impact of climate change on agricultural output in Sub-Saharan Africa and stimulates their economies against adverse consequences. To address these issues, the following research questions are raised.

1. Does climate change affect agricultural output in Sub-Saharan Africa?
2. Does climate change affect economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa?
3. What have been the contributions of agriculture to the Sub-Saharan African economies?

Researchers in search of solutions to these questions have delved into this study to assess the impact of climate change, in terms of temperature rise and rainfall, on agricultural output, food security and economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. Climate change continues to remain one of the vital and controversial issues in global forums. The world is now reeling under COVID-19, and it is expected that once it ends or partially ends, the new

normal of the world will be different. COVID-19 is going to have implications on agriculture, food security, and the economic and social structures of nations. The COVID-19 pandemic coupled with climate change has pushed for unprecedented social and economic changes in many economies. The environmental impact of the digital revolution and digital waste has become a major issue. A recent study has also found a correlation between climate indicators and the COVID-19 pandemic (Bashir et al., 2020). In the post-COVID-19 era, there are going to be numerous new issues and challenges about climate change.

Other parts of this paper are organised into four sections. The second section is a review of relevant literature; the third section discusses the methodology; the fourth section presents and discusses results; the last section contains a summary, recommendations and conclusion.

Review of Literature

Climate change manifests itself with temperature increases, changes in precipitation and rise in sea levels, thereby increasing the intensity of natural hazards like storms, floods and droughts (Pachauri and Reisinger, 2007). Food security is both directly and indirectly linked with climate change. Studies have shown that climate change could reduce crop yield; and areas vulnerable to drought could become marginal for cultivation, thus posing a threat to national food security and export earnings (Abul et al., 2011; Anupama, 2014). Increasing temperatures will result in enhanced evapo-transpiration, leading to a reduction in water availability. An increase in the magnitudes of the storms will increase the frequency of floods and flood damage, which, in turn, will increase salt intrusion, causing less amount of water available for agricultural use. According to Adejuwon (2004), the issue of climate change has become more threatening not just for the sustainable development of socio-economic and agricultural activities of individual nations but for humanity as a whole. Overcoming the challenges posed by climate change related to agricultural production, which, in turn, affects economic development, will depend on farmers' use of clean technology (Kurukulasuriya and Mendelsohn, 2007; Hassan and Nhemachena, 2008).

While assessing the impact of climate change on African cropland from eleven countries involving over 9,000 farmers, Kurukulasuriya and Mendelsohn (2006) found that net farm revenues fall as precipitation falls or as temperatures warm across all the surveyed farms. Edame et al. (2011) examine the economic impacts of climate change on food security and agricultural productivity in Sub-Saharan Africa. They noted that agriculture is particularly vulnerable to climate change. Projections to 2050 suggest both an increase in global mean temperatures and increased weather variability, with

implications for the type and distribution of agricultural production worldwide. They further stated that increased intensity and frequency of storms, altered hydrological cycles and precipitation variance have long-term implications on the viability of current world agro-ecosystems and future food availability.

World agriculture faces a serious decline within this century due to global warming. Overall, agricultural productivity for the entire world is projected to decline between 3 per cent and 16 per cent by 2080 (Anupama, 2014). Developing countries, many of which have average temperatures that are already near or above crop tolerance levels, are predicted to suffer an average of 10–25 per cent decline in agricultural productivity in the 2080s. Rich countries, which have typically lower average temperatures, will experience a much milder or even positive average effect, ranging from an 8 per cent increase in productivity to a 6 per cent decline. Individual developing countries face even larger declines. India, for example, could see a drop of 30–40 per cent (Ochieng, Kirimi and Mathenge, 2016).

Ubachukwu (2005) and Efe (2009) studied the threat of climate change to food security and livelihood in selected states of Nigeria. Their findings showed that climate change posed adverse effects on food productivity in Nigeria. The studies showed that climate change significantly impacts all aspects of crop yields, availability of seeds, and access and utilisation of foods. They noted that there were decreases in crop yields due to decreases in temperatures in the study areas and that most of the farmers had low levels of awareness of the dangers of climate change.

Food security is both directly and indirectly linked to climate change. Any alteration in climatic parameters, such as temperature and humidity that govern crop growth, has a direct impact on the quantity of food produced. Indirect linkage pertains to catastrophic events like floods and droughts, which are projected to multiply as a consequence of climate change, leading to huge crop loss and leaving large patches of arable land unfit for cultivation and hence threatening food security. The net impact of food security will depend on the exposure to global environmental change and the capacity to cope with and recover from global environmental change. At a global level, increasingly unpredictable weather patterns will lead to a fall in agricultural production and higher food prices, leading to food insecurity, which can be treated as an indicator to assess vulnerability to extreme events and slow-onset changes. This impact of global warming has significant consequences for agricultural production and trade of developing countries, as well as an increased risk of hunger. The number of people suffering from chronic hunger has increased from under 800 million in 1996 to over 1 billion recently. United Nations population data and projections (UNDP, 2009) show the global population reaching 9.1 billion by 2050, an increase of 32 per cent from 2010.

Osakhede et al. (2016) noted that climate change had constituted a great threat to rural and urban socio-economic landscapes as well as the implementation of scientific findings towards the advancement of community development in Nigeria and other African countries. It is shaping the natural landscape in the long run and the modern plan for rural and urban social and economic environments. This, unfortunately, has become a new reality with harmful effects. Many elements of the environment in the urban and rural and human society are sensitive to climate variability and change. Examples of climate-sensitive systems are ecosystems, agriculture, water needs and supply, and food production, among others.

Odejimi and Ozor (2019) use the Ordinary Least Square technique for the period of 1981–2017 to reveal that the impact climate change has, on agricultural production, has a positive relationship with government expenditure, exchange rate, rainfall and agricultural output while a negative relationship with temperature and inflation.

Odusola and Abidoye (2015) examined the impact of temperature and rainfall volatility on economic growth in 46 African countries. They employed the Bayesian hierarchical modelling approach, which allowed them to estimate both the country-level and Africa-wide impact of climate change—an extreme event on economic growth in Africa. The finding shows that a 1° Celsius increase in temperature leads to a 1.58 per cent points decline in economic growth while temperature shock reduces economic growth by 3.22 percentage points. A one-per-cent change or shock in rainfall leads to a 6.7 per cent change in economic growth. The impact of temperature changes across the 46 countries ranges from -1.24 per cent to -1.82 per cent in Gross Domestic Product (GDP). There are proximity effects on the impact.

Zhai et al. (2009) examined the potential long-term effects of global climate change on agricultural production and trade in China. Utilising an economy-wide, global Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) model as well as simulation scenarios of how global agricultural productivity may be affected by climate change up to 2080, the study suggested that, with a declining share of agriculture in GDP, the impact of climate change on the overall macro economy may be moderate. Umar (2008) noted that the effects of global warming and climate change in Nigeria are currently of concern to governments, institutions, environmentalists and firms. They noted that the effects of climate change in the country generally manifests as shifting weather variations or patterns involving unprecedented and overall changes in weather patterns, excessively heavy precipitation, unusual high temperature, propelling significant changes in different parts of the country, rising sea levels, the disappearance of the coastal strips and noticeable increases in the frequency of some extreme weather events in the country. The study concluded by recommending that governments have a big role in

disseminating information on the potential and actual impacts of climate change as well as on forecast impacts on agriculture, water resources and diseases.

Gaps in Studies

1. Most studies deal with the nexus of two variables of climate change and economic growth, as can be seen in the study by Osakhede et al. (2016). This study, however, looks at the interaction between climate change and food security.
2. Single equation models are specified in most studies. For example, in Olutoye and Olutoye (2014) and Odejimi and Ozor (2019). In this study, a system of equations was specified using Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) method of analyses for robust policy recommendations and forecast/simulation outputs.

Methodology

Model Specification

This study adopts a panel data framework. The use of panel data enables us to account for and isolate the effects of countries' specific time-unchanging characteristics, specifically the level of development. Furthermore, Wooldridge (2002) shows the relevance of using panel data to solve the problem of omitted variables. The combination of both cross-sectional and time-series data for different countries is important to avoid harmful over-generalisations.

The conventional form of panel data framework is given as:

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_i X_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$\mu_{it} = \mu_i + \nu_t + \varepsilon_{i,t}, \quad (2)$$

Where,

y_{it} is the dependent variable, while α_i, β_i and X_{it} are k-vectors of non-constant regressors and parameters for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ cross-sectional units (here countries) and $t = 1, 2 \dots T$ is time series unit

μ_{it} is the general disturbance, with μ_i , the country's, unobservable effect, ν_t , a time-specific factor and $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ an idiosyncratic disturbance

Climate change is captured by temperature and rainfall variables as demonstrated in Kumar and Gautam (2014). In the development equation, agricultural output is taken as the dependent variable, while inflation, exchange rate, capital formation and labour force are also included as

independent variables. The dynamic relationship is based on the fact that climate change may not only exert one round of effect on agricultural output or development; rather, the effects may be self-reinforcing over time (Ayinde et al., 2011).

$$AGOP = f(TEMP, RFALL, GEA, INF, EXR, GFCF, LABF) \quad (3)$$

Using the conventional form of panel data framework, equation (3) becomes:

$$AGOP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TEMP_{it} + \beta_2 RFALL_{it} + \beta_3 GEA_{it} + \beta_4 INF_{it} + \beta_5 EXR_{it} + \beta_6 GFCF_{it} + \beta_7 LABF_{it} + U_{it} \quad (4)$$

Where,

AGOP = Agricultural Output

CROP = Crop Production

TEMP = Average Annual Temperature

RFALL = Rainfall

GEA = Government Expenditure on Agriculture

INF = Inflation Rate (measured as the consumer price index)

EXR = Exchange Rate

GFCF = Gross Fixed Capital Formation

LABF = Labour Force

Introducing the control variable, such as the country's level of development, captured by RGDP per capita (RGDPpc), equation 4 becomes:

$$AGOP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TEMP_{it} + \beta_2 RFALL_{it} + \beta_3 GEA_{it} + \beta_4 INF_{it} + \beta_5 EXR_{it} + \beta_6 GFCF_{it} + \beta_7 LABF_{it} + \beta_8 RGDPpc_{it} + U_{it} \quad (5)$$

RDGPPc = Real Gross Domestic product per capita (measure of development)

The estimation of the above model was done by engaging the single equation linear GMM. As compared to some other models like the Panel Least Square (PLS) and Maximum Likelihood (MLE), GMM has been widely used in the estimation of models as it does not necessitate full knowledge of the data distribution. GMM also can correct the problems of endogeneity, heteroscedasticity and cross-sectional dependency that are common in panel data framework (Sarafidis, 2008; Sarafidis et al., 2008). The consistency of the GMM estimator, however, depends on the validity of the instruments, and this is usually addressed using the Sargen/Hansen test of over-identifying restrictions.

Data Sources

The data for the study was obtained from the World Bank (World Development Indicators) and a country-specific database for 17 countries in Sub-Saharan Africa—Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda (East Africa), Angola, Botswana, Congo DR, Lesotho, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa (Southern Africa), Cote d'Ivoire, Ghana, Liberia, Nigeria, and Sierra Leone (West Africa). The selection of the countries was rooted in the availability of data, and at the same time, it was ensured that different parts of Sub-Saharan Africa (Central, Eastern, Southern and Western) were covered in the study. This study covers the period 2011–2020 on an annual basis using a three-time series panel given the limitation of data for climate change analysis.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics of the data used in the analysis are presented in Table 1. The average growth rate of RGDPpc for the period is 1.63 per cent, which is quite low, although the maximum average value of 11.75 per cent growth rate indicates that there were some years with very impressive per capita growth rate figures. On the other hand, the minimum value of -9.89 also indicates that the income per capita figures was very low in certain years. The data shows that GDP per capita has been very unsteady in the country. This is supported by the high standard deviation of the variable at 4.27 when compared to the mean value. GDP per capita has varied significantly over the years in Nigeria, thereby indicating that the welfare and poverty reduction composition of the economy is highly unsteady. Indeed, there may be a steady rise in the per capita GDP for most of the years; yet, the rate of growth has been highly unsteady. The J-B statistic fails the significance test, which shows that GDPpc is normally distributed.

The average growth rate of AGOP is 5.88, which is high and suggests that agricultural output has performed well in the country over the years. Although there were periods of negative growth rates (as shown by the minimum value of -4.38), the average value indicates that the agricultural sector has been one of the best performing sectors over the past three decades. The standard deviation is, however, large and shows a significant level of instability in the growth rate, while the skewness of 4.46 shows that most of the data series was to the left of the mean, meaning they are lower than the reported mean value.

Table I: Descriptive Statistics (Results from E-Views)

Variable	Mean	Max.	Min.	SD	Skew	Kurt.	J-B	Prob.
RGDPPC	1.63	11.75	-9.89	4.27	-0.10	3.30	0.20	0.91
AGOP	5.88	55.58	-4.38	9.18	4.46	24.72	849.6	0.00
GEA	15.56	65.40	0.01	18.90	1.01	2.79	6.34	0.04
RFALL	93.95	112.25	72.07	8.31	-0.41	3.08	1.04	0.60
TEMP	27.22	27.86	26.52	0.32	0.04	2.48	0.43	0.81
GFCF	32.76	945.34	-36.40	156.58	5.56	32.94	1572.94	0.00
LABF	0.24	4.49	-2.73	1.15	0.95	7.25	33.35	0.00
EXR	93.749	306.921	0.672	90.735	0.826	3.022	4.208	0.122
INF	64.169	111.72	35.2	20.646	0.812	2.616	4.29	0.117

Source: Author's computation using E-Views

During the study period, average rainfall was 93.95 millimetres, with a standard deviation of 8.31, indicating variability over the years. This aspect of the focus on climate change influences, in particular, economic characteristics. The focus on variability rather than levels has been a major issue argued by researchers who observe that it is variability in a climate that imposes significant constraints on agricultural activities (Chen, et al., 2016; Moore, et al., 2017; Agarwal et al., 2019). The average temperature was 27.22 degrees Celsius for the period. The standard deviation of 0.32 is very low (though not many temperature changes are expected for less than 40 years). However, the temperature has experienced a level of variability. Indeed, the coefficient of variation for the temperature changes was over 600 per cent, which indicates a particularly worrisome process of temperature changes in Sub-Saharan Africa. The mean government expenditure on agriculture is 17.0 billion Naira, while the mean exchange rate is 93.74. The average growth rate of capital formation is 32.76 per cent, which is quite high, while the average growth rate of labour force participation rate is 0.24 per cent.

Unit Root Tests

Two tests of stationarity were employed in this study to analyse the stationarity status of the data series and indicate the presence or absence of unit-roots. Analysis for each of the two tests—Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillip-Peron (PP)—is performed with the trend and without the trend. This is because the datasets that include temperature variables may exhibit certain levels of trending that may affect the tests for stationarity (Sun et al., 2018). Moreover, the test results are presented in levels and first differences to determine, in comparative terms, the unit root among the time series and also to obtain more robust results.

Table 2: Unit Root Test for Variables

Variables	ADF test				P-P test				
	Without trend		With trend		Without trend		With trend		Order
	Levels	First Difference	Levels	First Difference	Levels	First Difference	Levels	First Difference	
LGDPPC	1.954	-45.14*	-2.031	-39.36*	1.137	-37.67*	-1.325	-33.76*	I(1)
LGOP	-2.329	-6.155*	-2.064	-5.775*	-2.298	-6.157*	-2.101	-5.772*	I(1)
LGEA	-0.002	-5.393*	-2.156	-6.834*	-0.002	-6.393*	-1.878	-14.45*	I(1)
LTEMP	-1.91	-8.57*	-2.15	-8.453*	-1.97	-10.90*	-4.83*	-10.62*	I(1)
LRFALL	-2.10	-12.00*	-2.66	-11.83*	-2.18	-18.67	-5.17	-17.38*	I(1)
LEXR	-1.054	-4.449*	-1.481	-6.004*	-0.883	-6.836	-1.782	-5.322*	I(1)
LINF	-1.74	-5.887*	-2.032	-3.622*	-1.174	-10.47*	-1.482	-9.043*	I(1)
LGFCF	-1.003	-4.924*	-4.42*	-6.494*	-1.376	-8.372*	-1.281	-7.442*	I(1)
LLABF	-1.374	-6.266*	0.132	-5.374*	-1.366	-7.843*	-1.329	-7.373*	I(1)

Note: * indicates significant at 5 per cent | **Source:** Author's computations using E-views

Table 2 presents the results of ADF and PP tests in levels and first differences. The results indicate that each of the variables (apart from the climate change variables) possesses both ADF and PP values that are less than the 95 per cent critical values for the level series and greater than the critical value for the differenced series. In most cases, the variables in level form were non-stationary but their first differences were found to be stationary. However, the variables of climate change were stationary in levels since their tests show the significance of both the ADF and PP in the levels form. This shows that all variables are integrated at order 1 (i.e. I[1]).

Panel Co-Integration Test

We further conducted a panel co-integration test to confirm if the variables had long-run relationships using the Kao co-integration test. The Kao test presented in Table 3 reveals that there is co-integration and long-run relationship between all the variables in the model. The null hypothesis of no co-integration is rejected at the 5 per cent level of significance, indicating co-integration among the variables.

Table 3: Kao Co-Integration Test

Null Hypothesis: No co-integration		
	t-Statistic	Prob.
ADF	1.940174	0.0262
Residual variance	4662.212	
HAC variance	456.1776	

Source: Author's computations using E-views

The GMM Estimation Results

The model was found to pass the Hansen (1992) test of valid instrument and the null hypothesis was accepted that all instruments are valid given Hansen/J statistics of 4.636442 and a probability of (0.052112) as shown in Table 5.

Table 4: Results GMM Estimates

Explanatory variables	Coefficient/Standard Error
TEMP	-0.018129/0.003813*
RFALL	0.002186/0.001155*
GEA	0.002614/0.000562*
INF	-0.001610/7.79E-05*
EXR	-0.000518/0.000351

Table 4 Continued

Explanatory variables	Coefficient/Standard Error
GFCF	0.004781/0.000682*
LABF	0.004684/0.000742*
RGDPPC	-2.42E-05/1.18E-05*
C	0.583360/0.014274

Hansen test = 4.636442

(0.052112)

Instrument rank = 11

$R^2 = 0.6752411$

Adj $R^2 = 0.592332$

DW = 1.321442

Number of observations = 47

Source: *Author's computation using E-Views*

The fitness of the model was examined, and the model was found to be well-fitted given an R^2 of 0.6752411, indicating that 68 per cent of the variation in the dependent variable was accounted for by the explanatory variables. The DW statistics is 1.321442. This, however, does not jeopardise the model, given that the use of the GMM method of estimation can also correct the problem of heteroscedasticity and serial correlation that may be present in the model.

Examining the relationship and impact of the independent variables, the result showed that TEMP, INF and EXR came with a negative significant impact on AGOP in line with theoretical expectation, while RFALL, GFCF, GEA and LABF showed a positive significant impact on AGOP. The relationship of these variables with AGOP was found significant indicating that policy measures towards reducing the effect of climate change on food security through AGOP should focus on these variables. The substantial impact of GFCF and LABF point to the need of enhancing the gross fixed capital formation and labour force because these variables give more opportunity to be financially and technologically developed and as well as the opportunity to secure better human capital development for better-paid jobs for higher level of income. Rainfall posed a significant impact on AGOP. Hence, seasonal variation is germane and was found to have a major impact on food security. All-round season agriculture powered by technology would be the best option for Sub-Saharan economies. The result also showed that inflation came with a negative noteworthy impact on AGOP.

Implications of the Findings and Policy Inferences

1. The outcome of the study exhibited a negative and substantial impact of climate change on agricultural output and food security. Rainfall posed a significant impact on AGOP. Hence, seasonal variation is germane and was found to have a major impact on food security. All-round season agriculture powered by technology would be the best option for Sub-Saharan economies.
2. The results also showed that growth in government expenditure on agriculture significantly affected output and food security. Hence, a continued upsurge in government expenditure is highly recommended, especially in the development of hybrid yields.
3. The level of development in these countries was also established to increase agricultural output, thereby improving food security. Food security has also been found to increase the level of economic development of the affected countries.

Summary, Recommendation and Conclusion

Summary

From the empirical analysis, the following findings were reported:

1. Climate change has a varied effect on agricultural production in Sub-Saharan Africa based on climatic factors considered (temperature or rainfall) or the agricultural activity involved. In general, temperature has more effect on agricultural production than rainfall.
2. At lower levels of rainfall, agricultural production is low. An increase in rainfall leads to rise in agricultural production.
3. Climate change has an unequivocal deleterious effect on agricultural production, both in the short run and in the long run. The elasticity of the long-run impact of rainfall on agricultural production was shown to be close to one, indicating that any excess inches in rainfall would likely reduce food production by the same proportion. Temperature variations were shown to have debilitating impacts on agricultural production in Sub-Saharan Africa.
4. Climate change has an indirect and stable impact on economic growth through the agricultural production channel. Climate change tends to reduce the growth of the economy by limiting expansions—inadequate expenditure in input, infrastructure and R&D—in the agricultural sector of these economies. The effects of agricultural output and export as channels of climate change influences on economic growth are relatively similar. In

other words, when climatic conditions change, the shocks on both agricultural output and exportation have similar effects on economic growth in these countries.

5. Other factors such as government spending in agriculture, exchange rate, inflation, capital accumulation and labour input were also shown to have long-un impacts on agricultural production in Sub-Saharan Africa. This invariably affected food security.

Recommendations

Based on this study's findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are made. The general and particular findings in this study suggest some policy directions which may provide a basis for useful recommendations for the policy authorities.

1. Rainfall is expected to be unpredictable both in terms of periodicity and amount. This means that adaptation strategies for climate change should also consider both short- and long-term circumstances. The various Meteorological Service Authorities should put up early warning systems to monitor changes in the weather and guide farmers on the appropriate time to plant in cases of drought or flooding. Furthermore, they should focus on risk management in the most vulnerable areas and among the most vulnerable groups to reduce losses.
2. The study has also shown that agricultural spending can help to boost the sector's production in the long run. This means that if government expenditures can be directed at addressing climate impacts, the effects may be more profound on the agricultural sector. Thus, a strategic spending pattern, which helps detect early signs of climatic effects and enables a rapid response to short-term effects of climate change, is needed to boost agricultural production in the face of unstable climate conditions.
3. In order to prepare for the future in terms of climate change, there should be a strong focus on crop and animal breeding for the development of new climate-tolerant varieties. Therefore, agricultural research institutions need to provide strong support for climate-resilient crops and animal breeds that are suitable for the concerned countries.
4. For agricultural output, crop diversification can be done. For example, mixed cropping with several crops being grown simultaneously can help systems exhibit greater durability during periods of high water or heat stress to stimulate higher productivity.

Conclusion

This study focused on the relationship between climate change and food security in Sub-Saharan Africa. Both statistical and econometric techniques were employed in the analysis to show the direction of changes in climatic conditions as well as the pattern of relationships and effects on agricultural production and food security. Both the statistical and econometric procedures demonstrated that climate changes are becoming more profound in Sub-Saharan Africa with long-run effects on agricultural production. The empirical analysis showed that these patterns of effects have strong implications on economic performance in the long run.

Global warming and rapid changes in climate pose significant risks to almost all segments of livelihood. Thus, economic performances around the world are often skewed based on climatic occurrences. The aspect most affected in these cases is the agricultural sector, which depends on land and climatic elements for sustenance (especially in developing countries). In this study, the role of climate change is essentially debilitating to both agricultural production and food security, both in the short run and in the long run. Both mitigation and adaptation systems are suggested as the main responses to climate change and food security. Over time, however, there is a need for a strong and significant commitment around the world to reduce global warming and reduce the level of depletion of life on the planet. The findings from this study will be crucial for policymakers and national governments in Sub-Saharan Africa in the way forward to reduce gender inequality and accelerate financial inclusion.

References

- Abdul-Razak, M., & Kruse, S. (2017). The adaptive capacity of smallholder farmers to climate change in the Northern Region of Ghana. *Climate Risk Management*, 17, 104–122.
- Abul, Q. A., Leal, W., Trinxeria, J. M., Jaafar, A. H., & Ghani, Z. A. (2011). Assessing the impacts of climate change in the Malaysian agricultural sector and its influences in investment decision. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 7(2), 225–234.
- Adejuwon, S.A. (2004). Impact of climate variability and climate change on crop yield in Nigeria. Paper presented at the stakeholders' workshop on assessment of impacts and adaptation to climate change (AIACC), Conference Centre, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, 271–279.
- Agarwal, A., Caesar, L., Marwan, N., Maheswaran, R., Merz, B., & Kurths, J. (2019). Network-based identification and characterization of teleconnections on different scales. *Sci Rep*, 9, 8808. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-45423-5>

- Anupama, M. (2014). Climate change and its impact on agriculture. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 4(4), 2250–3153. https://www.nswai.org/docs/Climate_change_impact_on_Agriculture.pdf
- Asian Development Bank (2020). *Nigeria economic outlook 2020*: Abidjan (Cote d'Ivoire), African Development Bank.
- Ayinde, O. E., Muchie, M., & Olatunji, G. B. (2011). Effect of climate change on agricultural productivity in Nigeria: A co-integration model approach. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 35(3), 189–194. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09709274.2011.11906406>
- Bashir, M. F., Ma, B., Komal, B., Bashir, M. A., Tan, D., & Bashir, M. (2020). Correlation between climate indicators and COVID-19 pandemic in New York, USA. *Science of the Total Environment*, 138835. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138835>
- Chen, S., Chen, X., & Xu, J., (2016). Impacts of climate change on agriculture: Evidence from China. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2015.01.005>
- Ebele, N. E. and Emodi, N. V. (2016), Climate change and its impact in Nigerian economy. *Journal of Scientific Research and Reports*, 10(6), 1–13. <http://www.journaljsrr.com/index.php/JSRR/article/view/21917/40737>
- Edame, G. E., Anam, B., Ekpenyong, W., Fonta, M., & Duru, E. J. C. (2011) Climate change, food security and agricultural productivity in Africa: Issues and policy directions. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 1(21) (Special Issue December).
- Efe, S. I. (2009). Climate change and food security in African: Delta state Nigeria experience. In R.N.C. Anyadike, L.A. Madu, & C.K. Ajaero (Eds), *Conference proceeding on climate change and the Nigerian environment*, Nsukka, 29 June–2 July, 105–126.
- Ezemonye L. I. (2019). Pandora's box of emerging environmental threats: Effects, policy and institutional reforms. *Greening Academia/Industry Research Synergy, Research Day and Conference*, Igbinedion University Okada, Edo State Nigeria.
- Food and Agriculture Organization, International Fund for Agricultural Development, & World Food Programme (FAO, IFAD, & WFP) (2015). *The state of food insecurity in the world 2015. Meeting the 2015 international hunger targets: Taking stock of uneven progress*. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i4671e.pdf>

- Hansen, B. (1992). Tests for parameter instability, in regressions with I(1) processes. *Journal of Business and Economic Statistics*, 10, 321–336.
- Hassan, R., & Nhemachena, C. (2008), Determinants of African farmers' strategies for adapting to climate change: Multinomial choice analysis. *African Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics*, 2(1), 83–104.
- Kumar, R., & Gautam, H. R. (2014) Climate change and its impact on agricultural productivity in India. *J. Climatol, Weather Forecasting*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2332-2594.1000109>
- Kurukulasuriya, P., & Mendelsohn, R. (2006), Crop selection: Adapting to climate change in Africa. Centre for Environmental Economics and Policy in Africa (CEEPA), Discussion Paper No. 26. University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa.
- Kurukulasuriya, P., & Mendelsohn, R. (2007), A Ricardian analysis of the impact of climate change on Africa Cropland. World Bank Policy Research Paper No. 4305, World Bank, Washington D.C.
- Moore, F. C., Baldos, U. L., & Hertel, T. (2017), Economic impacts of climate change on agriculture: A comparison of process-based and statistical yield models. *Environmental Research Letters*, 12(6), 1–9.
- National Centre for Disease Control (2020). COVID-19 outbreak in Nigeria: Situation report. <http://covid19.ncdc.gov.ng>
- Ochieng, J., Kirimi, L., & Mathenge, M. (2016), Effects of climate variability and change on agricultural production: The case of small-scale farmers in Kenya. *NJAS - Wageningen Journal of Life Sciences*, 77, 71–78. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.njas.2016.03.005>
- Odejimi, O. D., & Ozor, P. L. (2019), Can climate change affect agricultural output in Nigeria? *European Journal of Business and Management*, 11(6), 61–67.
- Odusola, A., & Abidoyo, B. (2015), Effects of temperature and rainfall shocks on economic growth in Africa. Paper presented at the 29th Triennial Conference of the International Association of Agricultural Economists (IAAE) 8–14 Published, 20 January, 1–25.
- Olutoye E., A., & Olutoye A. T. (2014). Assessing Agricultural resource and Nigerian Economic Growth. *Journal for Finance of Micro, Small & Medium Scale Enterprise in Nigeria*, 22, 371–381
- Osakhede, K. O., Ijimakinwa, S. O., & Adesanya, T. O. (2016), Climate change and its impacts on the development of coastal communities in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 2 (9).

- Pachauri, R. K., & Reisinger, A. (Eds) (2007), Synthesis report in, contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.
- Sarafidis, V. (2008), GMM estimation of short dynamic panel data models with error cross section dependence, March MPRA Paper No. 25176. <http://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/25176/>
- Sarafidis, V., Yamagata, T., & Robertson, D (2008), A test of cross section dependence for a linear dynamic panel model with regressors. *Journal of Econometrics*, 148(2), 149–161. 10.1016/j.jeconom.2008.10.006
- Sun, F., Roderick, M. L., & Farquhar, G. D. (2018), Rainfall statistics, stationarity, and climate change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science*, 115(10), 2305–2310. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1705349115>
- Tiffin, R., & X. Irz (2006): Is agriculture the engine of growth? In: *Agricultural Economics*, 35(1): 79–89.
- Ubachukwu, N. N. (2005), Climate and agriculture in north-western Nigeria. Unpublished project, Nsukka, University of Nigeria.
- Umar, A. T. (2008). Global warming and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGS) in Nigeria: A way forward. Paper delivered at the 5th Annual Conference of the Association of Nigerian Geographers (ANG) at the University of Calabar, 25–28 August, 47–55.
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (2020). COVID-19 pandemic: Humanity needs leadership and solidarity to defeat the coronavirus.
- World Bank (2020). Nigeria economic outlook 2020. Washington DC, World Bank.
- Worldometer (2020). World Population Prospects: The 2019 Revision. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division.
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2002) *Econometric analysis of cross-section and panel data*. The MIT Press.
- Zhai, F., Lin, T., & E. Byambdorj (2009). A general equilibrium analysis of the impact of climate change on agriculture in the People's Republic of China. *Asian Development Review*, 26(1), 206–225.

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